

COMMENTS - ANALYSIS OF THE INTERMEDIARY EFFECT OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUPPLY CHAIN FINANCE

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Abstract

Supply chain finance is a new type of financing method that has emerged with the development of the real economy. It is a new innovative activity that combines finance and supply chain. With the development of network technology, supply chain finance has become an important economic hotspot in today's society. It has also been further developed in manufacturing enterprises such as white goods companies and continuously penetrated into various industry fields. This paper describes the related content and relationship of blockchain technology and supply chain finance, and discusses the relationship between supply chain finance risk control, financial technology, application level of blockchain technology, and development level of supply by analyzing the effective questionnaire results of 137 regional heads of white goods supply chain in Chinese Mainland. Finally, opinions and suggestions are put forward on four aspects of supply chain finance risk control, financial technology, application level of blockchain technology, and development level of supply for white goods enterprises, which will serve as a reference for better utilizing blockchain technology to empower supply chain finance and promote the high-quality development of supply chain finance for white goods companies in the future.

Keywords: Supply Chain Finance, Blockchain Technology, Fintech, Risk Control, Information Sharing, Financing Costs, SME Financing, Decentralization, Structural Equation Modeling.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

In order to solve the bottleneck problem of enterprise development, the country has issued multiple policy documents to support and regulate the development of supply chain finance business, encouraging external funding supporters of supply chain enterprises and financial institutions to jointly participate in supply chain financing business, help enterprises overcome financing difficulties, and seek value returns for supply chain enterprises. Supply chain finance not only exists to solve the financing difficulties of enterprises, but also is not just a financial product and service. On the one hand, supply chain finance can utilize financial institutions or core enterprises to obtain financial support for financing enterprises. On the other hand, it can optimize the management of cash flow, information flow, and logistics in the supply chain, help the entire supply chain gain value, and enhance the competitiveness of upstream and downstream enterprises in the supply chain. Due to the different systems used by various enterprises in the supply chain, the entire industry chain information is not shared, and the information of each industry chain node cannot be fully connected. Due to risk control, supply chain financial service entities often only provide credit to primary suppliers and distributors of core enterprises. Supply chain finance cannot cover the entire industry chain. In supply chain finance business, capital flow is usually controlled through self compensation and closure. At

present, all supply chain finance businesses have been basically launched, and the ability to control fund flow has been improved. However, due to the large number of entities involved, payment settlement, contract performance and other processes cannot be automatically completed, making risk control for multiple entities more complex. Moral hazard issues such as misappropriation of funds, intentional breach of contract, and collusion still exist. These have greatly affected the normal performance of supply chain financing contracts.

Blockchain technology has unique technological advantages, and its integration with supply chain finance helps to build a more transparent and effective supply chain finance ecosystem. Promote the optimization of supply chain finance by improving system architecture, enhancing network trust, strengthening risk control, and improving service efficiency. The connection between blockchain technology and finance is very clever. From the perspective of supply chain finance, credit exchange is a key factor restricting its development. How to improve cooperation between fundraisers and donors? At present, blockchain technology has emerged, connecting high-tech with supply chain finance, whether it is accounts receivable, accounts receivable, prepayments or prepayments, or credit information that reflects the efficiency of supply chain financial services. Through the operation of blockchain technology, it consumes less funds, has strong security, and improves the financing efficiency of supply chain finance.

1.2 Statement Problem

The fundamental starting point of supply chain finance is to help core enterprises in the supply chain provide comprehensive credit endorsement services to relevant enterprises upstream and downstream of the industry, ultimately reducing the operating costs of the entire supply chain. We are rooted in the deep cooperation between financial capital and the real economy, aiming to build a mutually beneficial and sustainable industrial ecosystem between financial institutions, enterprises, and supply chains. The convenience and low cost of supply chain finance financing are the inherent driving forces for achieving industrial ecological prosperity. The development of supply chain finance in China is still in its early stages. There are problems such as poor information sharing and circulation, difficulty in penetrating credit for core enterprises in the upstream and downstream of the supply chain, and difficulty and high cost of financing for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Blockchain technology has technological features such as data unforgeability and information traceability, which have pioneering significance in improving the convenience of financing activities and reducing financing costs. Its decentralized, untrustworthy, and automatic clearing characteristics perfectly solve problems such as information asymmetry, lack of reliable centers, and complex settlement processes, thus demonstrating unprecedented potential in this field. As a major manufacturing country, China's annual accounts receivable and receipts amount to billions of yuan, with huge market demand. Therefore, innovation in the field of supply chain finance aims to reduce costs, release production capacity, and revitalize the capital turnover capacity of the entire manufacturing industry for small and medium-sized enterprises, which is of crucial practical significance for implementing the Made in China 2025 development strategy.

This article aims to systematically analyze the development background and current situation of supply chain finance, conduct in-depth research on the factors that affect the development of supply chain finance, clarify the key factors driving the growth of supply chain finance, and analyze the role of blockchain technology in this process. This study further clarifies the direction of supply chain finance development and reveals the key foundations in the process of supply chain financing development.

1.3 Research Questions

The research in this article includes the following five questions:

Question 1: What is the background and current development status of supply chain finance?

Question 2: What are the main factors affecting the development of supply chain finance

Question 3: How do various factors affect the development of supply chain finance?

Question 4: What is the role of blockchain technology in the development of supply chain finance?

Question 5: How to apply blockchain technology to the development of supply chain finance?

1.4 Research Objectives

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

Goal 1: Summarize the current development status of domestic supply chain finance in China over a period of time, and clarify the achievements and experiences achieved in the development process.

Goal 2: Identify the main factors driving and influencing the development of supply chain finance in China.

Goal 3: Clarify the level of supply chain development, the level of blockchain technology application, the level of blockchain technology application, and the risk control of supply chain finance between financial technology.

Goal 4: Clarify the application level of blockchain technology in the development of supply chain finance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Application Level of Blockchain Technology

Mao Lifei (2021) believes that the digitization of trade processes has the function of identifying and controlling risks, thereby helping to stabilize supply chain finance. Liu Xiaobin (2022) proposed through research that the lack of risk control models in commercial banks is an important reason for the existence of supply chain finance risks, and believes that the relevant risk control strategies of commercial banks are incomplete. Zhang Dan (2017) applied lifecycle theory to classify enterprises in the supply chain. After classification research, it has been found that enterprises in the classification management chain can not only more accurately locate

high-quality customers, but also help investors avoid related risks. Ke Yangning (2023) found that the unique characteristics of blockchain can help solve the problems of traditional supply chain finance, allowing blockchain technology to enter the field of supply chain finance, reducing overall operational risks, and improving efficiency. Zhong Yixian (2019) proposed a more comprehensive supply chain risk indicator evaluation system through research. Through model analysis, it was found that the application of new technologies such as blockchain technology can improve the risk monitoring level of commercial banks and promote the healthy development of supply chain finance. From a technical perspective, blockchain is a technology system maintained by multiple parties, storing data in blockchain links. Using cryptography to ensure transmission and access security, and achieving consistent storage of data, which is tamper proof and non repudiation.

2.2 Financial Technology

The core of fintech is to use technology as the overall driving force, apply technology to financial business, and thereby improve the efficiency of enterprises. Kohers and Kohers (2000) argue that fintech is a deep collaboration between financial and high-tech enterprises, which can help traditional finance expand its business scope and customer base. Arner et al. (2015) analyzed the connotation of financial technology from a technical perspective and believed that current financial technology mainly includes four major technologies: big data, blockchain, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence. Financial technology can organically combine these information technologies with finance to solve problems that traditional finance finds difficult to solve. Zavolokina et al. (2016) argue that fintech is a product of the integration of information technology and the financial industry, widely representing the development direction of digital finance.

Gomber et al. (2017) believed that financial technology combined Internet technology with financial services, not only enabled finance through technology, but also disrupted the existing system order. Chuen and Teo (2015) argue that fintech is the use of technological innovation to change the traditional financial industry structure and achieve financial innovation. The application of new technologies can drive traditional financial enterprises to upgrade their existing business models, optimize business processes, and develop new financial products. These innovations have expanded the business scope of traditional finance and also affected the entire financial market.

2.3 Development Level of Supply

Hofmann (2005) views supply chain financing as a new way for two or more institutions to create new value by planning, executing, and controlling to allow funds to flow between them. Berger&Udell (2006) emphasized the causal relationship between regulations issued by administrative agencies and economic structure, which can have a certain impact on the effectiveness and profitability of various loan methods. This approach will also have a certain degree of impact on the financing difficulties of small and medium-sized enterprises. The financial structure includes the existence and operational status of different types of financial institutions. Lending techniques include several transaction techniques and relational lending.

Moritz Leon Gomm (2010) proposed a framework for studying financial issues in logistics and supply chain management, and pointed out that studying financial issues from a supply chain perspective provides important opportunities for supply chain management professionals. Supply chain management, as a long neglected driver of shareholder value, not only helps to increase sales, sales costs, and investment capital, but also has the potential to increase capital ratio costs.

Lamoureux and Evans (2011) argue that supply chain finance is a financial ecosystem built around core enterprises. By leveraging the advantages of core enterprises, the overall optimization of funding for the entire ecosystem can be achieved, thereby maximizing the benefits of the entire ecosystem. Wuttke et al. (2013) argue that supply chain finance is an evolutionary form of reverse factoring that enables buyers to achieve real-time monitoring, control, and optimization of cash flows.

Antonella Moretto (2019) confirmed the potential value of comprehensive ratings, primarily targeting strategic suppliers, which display expected returns for all stakeholders and highlight potential challenges faced. Luca Mattia Gelsimino (2019) proposed that working capital requirements and financial costs are key parameters for evaluating the benefits of using multiple cash flow plans simultaneously.

2.4 Supply Chain Finance Risk Control

A sound risk control organizational system is the organizational guarantee for achieving comprehensive and full process risk control. It is also a complete risk control system and a fundamental carrier of scientific risk control processes. Due to the different risk characteristics between supply chain finance credit business and traditional credit business, it is necessary to establish an independent risk control system for risk control. An independent risk control system for supply chain finance business can make the overall operation of the risk control system more efficient. The main line of credit risk control is the good cooperative relationship between supply chain group enterprises. Advantageous industries and best-selling products are prerequisites for maintaining good cooperative relationships in the supply chain. It is also an important prerequisite for banks to effectively control credit risks in supply chain credit business. Banks should choose industries and products that can provide supply chain financing in advance, and take market access as the first line of defense to control supply chain credit risks before lending. The main reasons for operational risk are the failure of internal controls and personal violations. Due to the fact that post loan management is an important step in supply chain finance credit business, the probability of operational risk is higher than that of traditional business, which requires banks to establish dedicated departments responsible for post loan tracking and pledge management. Most of the pledge management processes are managed by logistics companies or warehousing companies, which requires logistics companies to continuously improve their warehousing management and information technology levels, develop comprehensive warehousing and delivery quality risk control plans, and strengthen their regulatory capabilities for high-quality goods. On the other hand, banks should carefully choose regulatory entities, establish strict operational norms and regulatory procedures to eliminate internal management loopholes and risks brought about by violations.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework

2.6 Hypothesis

- H1: Supply chain finance risk control affects development level of supply chain finance
- H2: Financial technology affects the development level of supply chain finance
- H3: The risk control level of supply chain finance is positively correlated with the application level of blockchain technology
- H4: The Financial technology is positively correlated with the application level of blockchain technology
- H5: The development level of blockchain technology is positively correlated with the development level of supply chain finance
- H6: Blockchain technology plays a mediating role in the impact of financial technology on the development of supply chain finance
- H7: Blockchain technology plays a mediating role in the impact of supply chain finance risk control on the development of supply chain financing

3.METHODOLOGY

This section introduces the methodology of this study, detailing the research tools and measures used to evaluate structures to ensure the reliability and effectiveness of the collected data.

3.1. Research Instrument and Data

This study uses questionnaire surveys as the main research tool to collect data, supplemented by interviews as auxiliary and supplementary.

Firstly, questionnaires were distributed to employees of white goods companies engaged in supply chain finance, and then five employees from an A-share listed company engaged in supply chain finance were selected for interviews.

The questionnaire survey is based on the questionnaire developed by Amabile (1996) and the organizational innovation scale designed for research. The interview was conducted using NViVO. NViVO is a powerful qualitative analysis software specifically designed for processing non data materials such as text, images, audio, and video.

It can process and analyze various types of data according to the user's ideas. By quickly analyzing common content in data, it can help users classify and organize it, enabling them to process data efficiently.

NViVO allows users to break free from the tedious manual tasks of previous data analysis processes, such as classification, sorting, and organization, giving them more time to explore development trends, establish theoretical models, and ultimately obtain conclusions about research questions. In addition, it also supports team collaboration, allowing multiple users to process and analyze data simultaneously, improving work efficiency.

3.2. Measures

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics is a statistical method used to summarize, organize, and simplify data. In this research questionnaire, six descriptive statistical questions were designed to inquire and analyze the basic personal information of participants, including seven aspects such as gender, age, and education level. Descriptive statistics mainly include statistical methods such as frequency allocation and percentage. Use statistical analysis to explain the distribution of demographic variables and further understand the correlation between variables. This study mainly uses frequency distribution and percentage from demographic data for statistics.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis is mainly used to determine whether the questionnaire is stable and reliable. It is generally believed that the testing procedure for quantitative variables is as follows: (1) After questionnaire collection, the load of each factor should be above 0.5, and p should only be less than 0.05. (2) Cronbach alpha should be greater than 0.7. (3) The combined reliability should be greater than 0.7. Use the above three standards to test the reliability of the scale. Qiu Haozheng (2006) believes that the higher the reliability, the more stable the scale will be in measuring the same concept.

Effectiveness Analysis

The validity mainly tests whether the scale has validity, accuracy, and correctness. Jiang Xiaohua (2010) believes that commonly used effectiveness indicators include six aspects: surface effectiveness, content effectiveness, relevance effectiveness, structural effectiveness, aggregated effectiveness, and discriminative effectiveness. There are many indicators of effectiveness, and generally speaking, the effectiveness of a scale mainly depends on three aspects: surface, content, and structure.

Structural Equation

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): This study used the Mplus editor 6.12 to analyze data, which can perform analysis of variance and SEM. This advanced statistical method was used in the final conceptual framework of the study to analyze the causal relationship between determinants and determinants. In these assumptions, the determining variable and the determining variable are interconnected. This method helped researchers form their theories. This study has also been successful. The reliability of any testing or measuring equipment is crucial. It directly affects the accuracy of test interpretation.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

This section introduces the data analysis and results of this study, outlines demographic information related to the respondents, evaluates measurement models to ensure their reliability and effectiveness, analyzes structural models to test proposed hypotheses, and determines the relationships between structures.

4.1 Demographic Information

As shown in Table 4.1, among the surveyed regional heads of white goods supply chain in Chinese Mainland, only one person is younger than 30 years old, accounting for 1.5%; There are 10 people aged 31 to 35, accounting for 7.3%; There are 15 people aged between 36 and 40, accounting for 10.9%; 35 people aged 41 to 45, accounting for 25.5%; 35 people aged 46 to 50, accounting for 25.5%; 40 people over 51 years old, accounting for 29.2%

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of Age (N=137)

	Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
Age	≤30 years old	2	1.5%
	31-35 years old	10	7.3%
	36-40 years old	15	10.9%
	41-45 years old	35	25.5%
	46-50 years old	35	25.5%
	51 years old	40	29.2%
	Total	137	100.0%
Gender	Male	100	73.0%
	Female	37	27.0%
	Total	137	100.0%
The high education	High school or below	-	-
	College	10	7.3%
	Bachelor's degree	71	51.8%
	Master's degree	56	40.9%
	Total	137	100.0%
Year of work	≤5 years old	2	1.5%
	6-10 years old	15	10.9%
	11-20 years old	57	41.6%
	21-30 years old	47	34.3%
	≥31 years old	16	11.7%
	Total	137	100.0%
Years of work experience as regional leader	≤5 years old	32	23.4%
	6-10 years old	35	25.5%
	11-20 years old	36	26.2%
	21-30 years old	28	20.4%
	≥31 years old	6	4.4%
	Total	137	100.0%
Years of tenure in current position	≤5 years old	85	62.0%
	6-10 years old	28	20.4%
	≥11 years old	24	17.5%
	Total	137	100.0%

4.2 Assessment of the Measurement Model

Table 4.2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.865
	Approx. Chi-Square	2135.128
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	46
	Sig.	.000

The test results indicate that the KMO test value of the survey data is 0.865, which is greater than 0.70, indicating that the questionnaire is suitable for factor analysis. Bartlett's sphericity test showed a chi square value of approximately 2135.128, which is greater than zero with a significance probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$).

Therefore, the null hypothesis of Bartlett's sphericity test was rejected, and the scale was considered suitable for factor analysis, thus having good structural validity.

Table 4.3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.866
	Approx. Chi-Square	2813.126
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	56
	Sig.	.000

The test results indicate that the KMO test value of the survey data is 0.866, which is greater than 0.70, indicating that the questionnaire is suitable for factor analysis. The results of Bartlett's sphericity test indicate that the chi square value is approximately 2813.126, indicating that the value is greater than zero with a significance probability of 0.000. ($p < 0.01$) indicates that the null hypothesis of Bartlett's sphericity test should be rejected. The results indicate that the scale is suitable for factor analysis and has good structural validity. This means that the variables in the scale are not completely correlated and have sufficient variability, making it suitable for factor analysis. Therefore, the results of factor analysis can be considered reliable and effective.

Table 4.4: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.896
	Approx. Chi-Square	2580.756
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	66
	Sig.	.000

The KMO test value of the survey data is 0.896, which is greater than 0.70, indicating that the questionnaire is suitable for factor analysis. The approximate chi square value is 2580.756, which is greater than zero and has a significant probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of Bartlett's sphericity test is rejected. The scale is considered suitable for factor analysis and therefore has good structural validity. Therefore, survey data can be regarded as reliable and effective data for factor analysis, which will help determine potential factors and their interrelationships. The results of factor analysis can be used to gain a deeper understanding of the tested structure and make informed decisions based on the analysis results.

Table 4.5: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.903
	Approx. Chi-Square	2486.794
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	66
	Sig.	.000

The KMO test value of the survey data is 0.903, which is greater than 0.70, indicating that the questionnaire is suitable for factor analysis. The approximate chi square value is 2486.794,

which is greater than zero and has a significant probability of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of Bartlett's sphericity test is rejected. The scale is considered suitable for factor analysis and therefore has good structural validity. Therefore, survey data can be regarded as reliable and effective data for factor analysis, which will help determine potential factors and their interrelationships. The results of factor analysis can be used to gain a deeper understanding of the tested structure and make informed decisions based on the analysis results.

4.3 Assessment of Structural Model

The Bootstrap method is used in this paper to test the mediating effect. When using the Bootstrap method, the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable is assumed to be c , the independent variable's effect on the mediating variable is a , the mediating variable's effect on the dependent variable is b , and the independent variable's direct effect on the dependent variable is c' . To proceed to the next step, the test coefficient c must be significant; if it is not significant, it indicates the presence of a masking effect, and the test is terminated. Second, test the coefficients a and b in turn; if they are significant, proceed to the next step; if at least one is not significant, the Bootstrap method should be used. ab , ab is not significant, indicating that the mediating effect is not significant, ab is significant, and the process proceeds to the next step.

The coefficient c' is then tested; if it is not significant, it means that it is fully mediated. If c' is significant, examine ab with the same sign as c' to determine the partial mediation effect; a different sign indicates the presence of masking (Wen, Zhonglin, & Ye, Baojuan, 2014). The Bootstrap method can be used to test the existence of the mediating effect directly. $H_0: ab=0$ is the hypothesis condition for the direct test. If the confidence interval derived from the test results contains zero, it indicates that no mediating effect exists. According to the path analysis results, the hypothesis test is valid, so we used the Bootstrap method in AMOS 22.0 and chose to repeat it 5000 times with a confidence interval criterion of 95%, so we used the syntax that comes with the AMOS software to assign all the relevant paths and calculate the standardized specific mediating effect. The Bootstrap method is a non-parametric approach that is widely used in mediation analysis to test the significance of indirect effects. By using this method, we can obtain a more accurate estimate of the standard error and confidence interval of the mediating effect.

Table 4.6: Results of Mediating Effect Test

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
Supply chain finance risk control - Application level of blockchain technology - Financial technology	.243	.164	.311	.000
Supply chain finance risk control - Application level of blockchain technology - Development level of supply	.231	.135	.247	.000
Application level of blockchain technology - Financial technology	.345	.214	.451	.000
Application level of blockchain technology - Development level of supply	.746	.643	.826	.000

5. DISCUSSION

From the objective of the research was to find out:

- 1) Summarize the current development status of domestic supply chain finance in China over a period of time, and clarify the achievements and experiences achieved in the development process.

Supply chain finance is a new field that has emerged with the development of the supply chain. It combines relevant knowledge of supply chain management and finance to handle funding issues in the supply chain. The role of supply chain finance is to coordinate the enterprises in the supply chain, effectively integrate logistics, information flow, and capital flow, reduce potential risks in the supply chain, and increase the profits of the entire supply chain. The research on supply chain finance is beneficial for the more rational allocation and utilization of resources, and promotes the development of China's economy.

China's supply chain finance started later than foreign countries, and the reform and opening up have led to the rapid development of China's manufacturing industry. Since 2010, China's manufacturing industry has steadily ranked first in the world. The development of China's manufacturing industry has attracted numerous international companies, and China has become an important part of the supply chain of many multinational corporations, promoting the rapid development of China's supply chain finance. Over the past few decades, China's supply chain finance has grown from scratch and combined with local characteristics to form a new development direction. Although supply chain finance has developed rapidly in the past few decades, there are still shortcomings at present. Many small and medium-sized enterprises have not been able to apply for relevant services and still face financial difficulties.

- 2) Identify the main factors driving and influencing the development of supply chain finance in China.

The main factors affecting the development of supply chain finance in China are supply chain finance risk control Financial technology, Application level of blockchain technology, Development level of supply. They have a direct impact and promoting effect on the development of China's supply chain finance. Supply chain finance risk control provides certain guarantees and warnings for the development of supply chain finance; Financial technology is the foundation of an enterprise, and it is the foundation of its existence; Application level of blockchain technology is an important driving force for the development of supply chain finance.

- 3) Clarify the Supply chain finance risk control between development level of supply, application level of blockchain technology, blockchain technology application level, and financial technology.

Use the Bootstrap method to test the intermediate role of blockchain technology in the development of supply chain finance. The results indicate that blockchain technology has a significant mediating effect on the development of supply chain finance

- 4) Clarify the application level of blockchain technology in the development of supply chain finance.

Blockchain technology can build efficient and trustworthy alliances, reshaping new supply chain models. Blockchain technology is a fusion innovation of existing technologies such as peer-to-peer networks, cryptography, consensus mechanisms, etc. It has application value in value transmission, trust building, and efficient collaboration.

Numerous enterprises and financial institutions in the supply chain can jointly build a trustworthy alliance ecosystem through blockchain technology, thereby achieving the effect of bridging information silos of data elements, accelerating information flow between alliances, and breaking down trust barriers. At the same time, financial institutions can verify the authenticity of trade background based on multi-dimensional information on the chain, expand refined and personalized innovative financial products, and give birth to new business models.

Blockchain technology can accelerate the circulation of credit vouchers and achieve cross level transmission of credit. Blockchain can help solve the problem of cross level credit transmission, helping core enterprises to issue and manage digital credit vouchers on the blockchain, such as the full process of opening, splitting, circulation, maturity redemption, account financing, and other deposit blockchain for core enterprise accounts receivable.

Unlike centralized systems, hash values in blocks ensure the immutability of data, while timestamps and transaction information recorded in blocks ensure the traceability of each transaction data. This characteristic of blockchain makes on chain transactions more trustworthy, accelerating credit cross level transmission to a certain extent, and is conducive to penetrating the credit of core enterprises to the end of the industrial chain.

Blockchain technology promotes the sharing of "four streams" of data and builds a trustworthy trade view. The decentralization, multi-party consensus, and transparency of blockchain technology can help core enterprises, financial institutions, and others jointly build an alliance chain, achieving information sharing, transparency, and traceability among alliance enterprises.

By connecting with the blockchain platform, various entities in supply chain finance, such as logistics, warehousing, financial institutions, and core enterprises, share key information related to supply chain trade, such as transaction information, goods information, warehousing information, and fund information.

This improves the timeliness of transaction chain information, connects information breakpoints, and provides strong support for accelerating the construction of a trustworthy and complete view of trade information.

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